

COOPERATION WITH NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS IN THE FIGHT AGAINST FOREIGN THREATS IN THE PROCESS OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article discusses the importance of the neighborhood institute and our intellectuals in the education of our children, the role of mass media, and the importance of our spiritual heritage in improving the spiritual and moral education of our youth.*

Keywords: *new society, self-management office, neighborhood, elder, family, tradition, socio-cultural, educational institutions, spiritual values, national identity.*

Elders and activists of the community, who are currently working effectively in our neighborhoods, making a significant contribution to turning this unique structure into a self-governing office, religious leaders of citizens' meetings the positive influence of experts on enlightenment and spiritual and moral issues is increasing more and more. It is these institutes that find their way to people's hearts, share their pains and concerns, and thanks to the timely practical help, correct and appropriate advice, peace and tranquility in the environment of the family and the neighborhood, and in the whole country. , our nation highly appreciates the growing feelings of mutual kindness. Looking at the issue from this point of view, [4,-B. 203-208] it is appropriate to pay attention to one of the important aspects of socio-cultural and educational institutions. [5,-B. 197-202] After all, socio-cultural and educational institutions are engaged in the assimilation and reproduction of cultural and social values, which are the basis for the implementation of the process of socialization of people. [6, p. 59]

Likewise, the contribution of enlightened fathers and mothers living in our families in the spiritual and moral education of our youth is also very important. Because our honorable president Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said: "We, according to the principle of every enlightened youth is a mentor to five young people," we want to attach our respected elders and mothers to the unorganized, unemployed youth who have difficult upbringing, need spiritual support we will continue to support the exemplary initiative aimed at:" - they emphasized. [1,-B. 238]

Indeed, these initiatives of our president will not fail to have a positive effect on the education of our youth. "We have the sacred task of raising a highly enlightened, full-potential generation. . In order to bring a perfect person to adulthood, first of all, it is necessary to raise the organic cooperation of the family, neighborhood, school, the whole society and the state to a higher level. Our children are extremely talented and second to none in terms of intelligence. It is the honorable duty of each of us to appreciate their talent, bring out their potential, and create conditions for raising them to be brave and selfless children of the Motherland. [3,-B. 78] In particular, we should respectfully recognize the important role played by these selfless, kind, passionate people in helping our young men and women to enter independent life, and for young families to find their rightful place in society.

While classifying social institutions according to their functions [7, P. 35-42]

first of all, it is necessary to pay attention to the importance of the family institution. Because it is one of the oldest among other institutions. [8, P. 11-12]

An atmosphere of affection in the family. Other norms in the family are implemented in accordance with the morals, customs and traditions accepted in the society. [9,-B. 59-60] For example, pre-marriage behavior, duties of a husband and his wife in the family, upbringing of children, family entertainment and other activities. [10, P. 1363-1367] A person who is deprived of this feeling will not be able to respect his relatives, compatriots, country, will not be able to do good to people. Love and sincerity in the family, attentiveness and care of family members to each other have a strong impact on the psyche of children, the manifestation of the child's emotions, the formation and fulfillment of his spiritual needs. provides ample opportunities for growth. All of us do not just belong to a special group of people who are busy with their work and live in the same house, but also to feel that our loved ones are in front of us, to feel their individuality, non-repetition, their special character, their moment. We feel the need to breathe in the general atmosphere of the family that creates our mothers. [11, P. 1373-1377] After all, the situations that occur in such a social environment, their direction, content and essence, the spiritual and moral views that occupy a priority place in society directly affect the formation of our children as perfect human beings. [12, P.6480-6487]

Parents should not lie to children in important situations of life. A child quickly perceives any kind of lies, deception, forgery with extraordinary sharpness, and when he notices it, he gets confused and tempted, drowns in suspicion. If something can't be said to a child, then it's better to always give the correct answer than to make up a silly statement and then pretend or lie and the child finds out. it is necessary not to go beyond a certain limit of avoidance or communication to the child. Never say, "You're too young to know that," or "You don't understand that anyway."

Such answers reflect the curiosity and selfishness in the child's heart. It is better to answer "I can't tell you this: everyone is obliged to keep certain secrets to themselves, it is not polite and not modest to interfere in the secrets of others." This does not harm the correctness and sincerity, and gives a clear lesson on duty, discipline and decency. [13, P. 417-421]

Parents should pay attention to the purity of family relationships. So, the family is a social institution that performs several functions. Among these functions, there is also the function of forming a worldview based on a system of ideas, values, and ideas strengthened within a certain ideology.

Good children follow in their father's footsteps, "The horse takes the place of the horse", respects their friends and loved ones, educates their brothers and sisters, and is kind to their relatives. These are the new fruits of the seed of spirituality that the father planted in his heart with love and hope. The good name left by the father is glorified by his children with their morals and manners, honest cocktails, respect and prestige among the people, and they make his soul happy. Deep study of our national values, traditions and the rich scientific heritage of our ancestors is important in the spiritual education of the young generation. There are no primary or secondary tasks for raising the morale of young people. All of them need to be in the same direction and in the center of constant attention and vigilance. Therefore, great importance is attached to education, knowledge and outlook. Just as the education of a child starts from the cradle, the beginning of spiritual perfection also starts from the family, kindergarten, school, higher education institutions, etc. If it is delayed, the more difficult it is to straighten a crooked plant without breaking it, the more difficult it is to achieve spiritual maturity.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted: "Wide use of information communication systems, the state is being organized in an electronic form, this is certainly good, in turn, it is an additional measure related to ensuring information security. "Life itself dictates watching events." [2, P. 46] This shows that development is a complex process with positive and negative aspects.

Today, the press and mass media are becoming such a powerful force that any people and nations thinking about their future cannot not feel it. [14, P. 445-449]

Mass media is the most basic, powerful and effective propaganda tool. Because the mass media serves as a unique educator of the public, an organizer of important events, and an effective tool for solving current problems. It is through mass media that our national values and universal values, national ideals and democratic principles are promoted. Mass media have always been a unique measure and indicator of democracy and freedom of speech. Free and independent mass media stimulate and strengthen democratic development.

Vitality is the main requirement for media activity today. It is necessary to evaluate how useful or harmful it is for propaganda if the given information consists mainly of showing achievements and praises. As long as there is life, it is natural that there will be problems, shortcomings, and defects. This is an axiom that does not require proof. Therefore, it is necessary to learn to look at the existence of problems as a normal thing, not as a tragedy. Seeing their presence and pretending not to see it can only cause harm. Therefore, it is necessary to recognize the problems in time and start solving them.

It is worth noting that the basis of propaganda is not only trust in the idea, but also trust in the person promoting the idea. Therefore, praise is not the only and even the most correct method of propaganda. Therefore, it is impossible to promote ideology only by praising life and describing it flawlessly.

Education is the main condition and guarantee of human maturity and development of the nation, a national issue under the control of the state and society. Education and training should be carried out in an inseparable harmony. The main goal and task of education is the education of a perfect person.

Our honorable president Sh.M. Mirziyoev said, "First of all, the historical and spiritual factor that will be the strong support and support of the strategy of New Uzbekistan, that is, our greatest wealth is the huge cultural heritage of our people, the existence of intellectual potential" [1, P. 238] did not point out for nothing.

Today, another powerful tool to eliminate the infiltration of the sharp one-sided, various destructive forces views, extremist and terrorist ideas that are completely alien to our traditions into our society, aimed at poisoning the minds of our youth, is the restoration of national values and national identity is to awaken a sense of awareness.

We consider the restoration of spiritual values to be a natural process of returning to our spiritual origins and roots from the realization of national identity. The spiritual values and cultural heritage of our people have served as a powerful source of spirituality for the peoples of the East for thousands of years. Therefore, we can say that these values are important in educating people, especially our youth, in the spirit of loyalty to their Motherland. [15, P. 74-76]

Our national and religious values are a powerful tool against the penetration of foreign ideas into the minds of our youth.

Human history has entered the 21st century. The 20th century took a place in history. Logically, mankind should have learned the relevant lessons from the past and not allow events that will be written down in history in the 21st century. Poverty, environmental problems, resource shortages, mass diseases, religious fanaticism and terrorism have been inherited from the 20th century into the 21st century. Moreover, as a result of the efforts of some forces, the list of dangers has expanded due to new ones. Dangers such as demographic crisis, export of democracy, spiritual impoverishment, information wars, and the imposition of Western lifestyle have increased the worries of the restive world.

In order to overcome such insidious threats, any society must have social qualities such as awareness, ideological security, integrity, combativeness, mobilization, general national unity. For this, it is necessary to always and everywhere use the methods of the national ideology to fight against foreign ideologies, including propaganda aimed at exposing the essence of destructive ideas, ideological monitoring and conveying the essence of threats to the minds and hearts of our people, spreading enlightenment against ignorance. will be done.

Directing and educating people to one or another goal is a two-way process. Propaganda subjects (propagandists, TV, radio, press) and objects of propaganda (person, population) participate in it. The effectiveness of propaganda and propaganda is known in the difference between the pre-propaganda and post-propaganda levels in the political consciousness of the people and the community. It will be possible to carry out changes in the ideology of the team based on scientific achievements, to determine and improve the effectiveness of propaganda and propaganda, achievements and shortcomings.

The effectiveness of ideological education first of all depends on the clear definition of what the result of ideological education of society should be. [16, P. 124-125].

The ideological immunity of each person, group, or society can be studied, evaluated, and improved based on five levels: In this case:

- the first, that is, the lower level of ideological immunity - the individual, team, society is not aware of the above knowledge; indifferent to destructive ideological ideas;
- the second level - there is knowledge, but it is not felt, not systematized, therefore it is not ready to use it against destructive ideological ideas;
- the third level - has ideological knowledge, but it is difficult for the individual and society to apply it theoretically;
- fourth level - has basic knowledge, can correctly assess the situation; has developed immunity against internal and external political and ideological influences and uses it consciously;
- the fifth - high level - has excellent ideological, political, economic knowledge and can easily apply this knowledge in practice and actively expose destructive ideological and political ideas everywhere.

The analysis shows that in the following years, some young people think of benefiting the nation, the Motherland, and the feeling of becoming a useful person in strengthening independence is not formed on a special, scientific basis. the feeling is manifested. At the same time, among some citizens, there are unpleasant manifestations such as moral limitation, narrow worldview, non-observance of national decency standards, gap between words and deeds, weakness of national pride, which should be eliminated together.

In conclusion, we can say that in the formation of the spirituality of our youth, we need to increase the importance and place of our enlightened mothers and fathers in the spiritual and moral

education of our youth. The social and cultural environment that expresses our national character in our country has the main influence on the stability of the family institution.

Thanks to the comprehensive attention paid to the stability of the family institution by our state, the fact that the family performs all its functions at a high level serves as a solid foundation for the development of our society.

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